

1 **Large lakes may moderate projected climate-change velocity in boreal North America**

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17

18 **Abstract**

19 The interior biomes of North America are projected to experience rapid climatic change,
20 particularly in relation to drought, yet climate exposure estimates remain highly uncertain in
21 northern regions with sparse weather-station coverage. Widely used gridded products
22 underrepresent climates shaped by large lakes, potentially biasing assessments of climate-change
23 vulnerability. We examined this issue in the lake-rich North American boreal biome by
24 comparing climate velocity in potential evapotranspiration (PET) across three contrasting climate
25 products. Across products, PET velocity was driven primarily by baseline climate representation
26 and downscaling method, whereas differences among global climate models (GCMs) were
27 minor. Model-based products (ERA5 and CRCM5) produced substantially lower velocities than
28 the station-interpolated ClimateNA baseline because they captured stronger spatial temperature
29 gradients—especially around large lakes—and weaker temporal gradients. Dynamical
30 downscaling further reduced temporal gradients near lakes but had limited influence on overall
31 velocity patterns. These results demonstrate that commonly used station-based products may
32 overestimate climate velocity in lake-rich northern regions. In contrast, model-based baselines
33 that incorporate reanalysis and lake–atmosphere interactions better represent spatial climate
34 heterogeneity and reveal extensive areas of low climate velocity associated with large lakes.
35 Such areas are strong candidates for climate-change refugia, suggesting that lake-mediated
36 buffering plays a larger role in moderating climate exposure across the boreal biome than is
37 typically recognized.

38

39

40 **Keywords**

41 Regional climate model, downscaling methods, reanalysis data, climate velocity, climate-change
42 refugia, boreal lakes, lake-atmosphere interactions, potential evapotranspiration

43

44 **Plain language summary**

45 Climate change is expected to increase drought stress across North America's boreal forest, but
46 estimates of how fast conditions are changing depend on the climate data used. In northern
47 regions, weather stations are sparse, and many commonly used datasets do not fully capture the
48 influence of large lakes. We compared different climate datasets and found that those based on
49 weather stations tend to estimate faster rates of climate change than products that simulate
50 physical processes, including lake-atmosphere interactions. In particular, areas near large lakes
51 showed slower rates of change when lakes were explicitly represented. This suggests that large
52 lakes may help buffer nearby ecosystems from climate change, making these areas important
53 potential refuges for species. It also highlights the importance of using appropriate climate data
54 in northern regions.

55

56 **Introduction**

57 Climate change is projected to result in broad-scale biome shifts, including especially dramatic
58 shifts in the relatively flat interior regions of the North American boreal region (Rehfeldt et al.
59 2012). Climate exposure metrics, such as climate velocity (Loarie et al. 2007), rank the boreal
60 biome as among the most climate-vulnerable regions in North America (Hamann et al. 2014,
61 Carroll et al. 2017). Dominated by coniferous trees, boreal forests are highly susceptible to
62 drought stress, driven largely by increasing temperature and evaporative demand (often
63 summarized by potential evapotranspiration, PET). Drought can reduce productivity (Song et al.
64 2021) and promote transitions to deciduous forest or non-forest conditions (Scheffer et al. 2012,
65 Frelich et al. 2021, Stralberg et al. 2018). Along southern margins, particularly in western
66 regions already near a moisture deficit, forest loss may intensify with climate change (Hogg
67 1997). Remote sensing studies have documented a northward shift in boreal forest extent, with
68 vegetation becoming less vigorous in the south and more productive in the north (Berner and
69 Goetz 2022, Rotbarth et al. 2023). However, observed patterns of vegetation change are
70 heterogeneous, reflecting disturbance, topo-edaphic conditions, and variability not well captured
71 by commonly used climate data.

72

73 Climate exposure metrics are typically derived from global climate models (GCMs), most often
74 using statistically downscaled projections. Statistical downscaling typically involves applying
75 smoothed GCM anomalies (future minus historical climate) to high-resolution baseline
76 climatologies derived from interpolated and topographically adjusted weather station data (e.g.,
77 [ClimateNA/SA/EU](#), [WorldClim](#), [DAYMET](#)). The appeal of such products lies in their ~1-km
78 resolution, generated using algorithms such as ANUSPLIN (Hutchinson et al. 1991, Hijmans et

79 al. 2005, McKenney et al. 2006), PRISM (Daly et al. 1997, 2008), and elevation adjustments
80 (Wang et al. 2012, 2016). While such approaches perform well where weather-station coverage
81 is dense, accuracy declines in data-sparse regions—often with station spacing exceeding 100 km
82 (Daly 2006). The northern parts of North America suffer from sparse coverage due to its
83 remoteness and low population density (Essou et al. 2017).

84

85 In addition to sparse coverage of weather stations, the boreal region features numerous large
86 lakes formed by late Pleistocene glaciation—e.g., Great Slave Lake (the deepest in North America
87 at 614 m, surface area 27,200 km²), Great Bear Lake (31,153 km²), Lake Athabasca (7,850 km²),
88 and Lake Winnipeg (24,514 km²). Lake Superior, the world’s largest by surface area (82,103
89 km²), marks the southern boreal margin. Large lakes influence climate by absorbing heat in
90 summer and releasing it in winter, buffering air temperatures and moderating seasonal extremes
91 (Sellers et al. 1997, Irambona et al. 2016, Warren and Vermette 2022) while driving lake breezes
92 that transport cooler air inland (Hinkel and Nelson 2012). The extent of influence depends on
93 wind direction, lake fetch, and thermal contrast (Kopec 1967). For example, Lake Superior’s
94 shores can be up to 19.2 °C cooler than sites 100 km inland (Hillman and Nielsen 2023),
95 supporting disjunct populations of arctic and alpine plants (Given and Soper 1981; Hillman and
96 Nielsen 2024) and resistance to boreal forest transitions (Hillman and Nielsen 2025). Similar
97 cooling effects occur on other Great Lakes at more southern latitudes, influencing forest
98 composition (Goldblum and Rigg 2010), tree growth (Tremblay and Bégin 2000, Sun et al.
99 2021), and seed maturation (Meunier and Sirois 2007), and maintaining disjunct pockets of
100 boreal forest beyond its southern extent (Frelich 2002).

101

102 Beyond these major water bodies, Canada’s boreal region contains an estimated 1.5 million lakes
103 larger than 0.4 km² (State of Canada’s Forests 2004–2005). Such an abundance of lakes
104 introduces significant climatic heterogeneity not captured by interpolation-based products.
105 Although small-lake breezes typically penetrate less than the lake diameter (Segal et al. 1997,
106 Crosman and Horel 2012), the sheer abundance of smaller lakes across the boreal region
107 suggests potentially significant cumulative effects (Macdonald et al. 2006).

108

109 Lakeshore climates are poorly represented by weather stations (Hillman and Nielsen 2023, 2025)
110 and topographic downscaling methods (Hutchinson 2000, Daly et al. 2008). However, reanalysis
111 products provide an alternative to station-based interpolation. These techniques use data
112 assimilation to merge forecasts with observational data from satellites and other sources,
113 avoiding interpolation across unsampled terrain. Although coarser in resolution (10–30 km), they
114 produce spatially complete and physically consistent climate fields. ERA5 (Hersbach et al.
115 2020), for example, improves upon earlier reanalyses through updated vegetation inputs
116 (Boussetta et al. 2013), enhanced snowpack parameterization (Dutra et al. 2010), and inclusion
117 of inland water bodies using the FLake model (Mironov et al. 2010, Balsamo et al. 2012).
118 Statistically downscaled versions of ERA5 are also available (e.g., CHELSA; Karger et al.
119 2021).

120

121 Although reanalysis products improve baseline climate representation, accurately representing
122 lake influences in future projections requires models that explicitly simulate lake–atmosphere
123 processes—something most GCMs do not do. Although roughly half of CMIP5 GCMs include
124 dynamic lake simulations for the Laurentian Great Lakes, few resolve them at $\leq 1^\circ$ (Briley et al.

125 2021), and representation of other northern lakes remains limited or unclear. Regional climate
126 models (RCMs) have the potential to address this GCM limitation by dynamically simulating
127 climate processes at finer scales, incorporating detailed land cover and topography. Developed
128 within the international CORDEX framework (Giorgi et al. 2009), the fifth-generation Canadian
129 Regional Climate Model (CRCM5; Martynov et al. 2013, Šeparović et al. 2013) has been widely
130 applied in North America. CRCM5 incorporates parameterizations such as the Canadian Land
131 Surface Scheme (Verseghy 1991, 2009) and the FLake freshwater lake model (Mironov et al.
132 2010; Martynov et al. 2012), which enable it to account for the moderating influence of large
133 water bodies on local and regional temperatures.

134

135 To test the hypothesis that GCM projections overestimate climate-change vulnerability in lake-
136 rich regions, we compared climate velocity—defined as the rate at which species or ecosystems
137 must move to maintain constant climate conditions (Loarie et al. 2009)—across climate-change
138 projections differing in baseline representation (weather-station vs. reanalysis) and downscaling
139 approach (statistical vs. dynamical). We focused on annual potential evapotranspiration (PET), a
140 temperature-driven indicator of atmospheric drying power and a key component of the climate
141 moisture index ($CMI = \text{precipitation} - PET$; Hogg 1997). PET strongly influences drought stress
142 in boreal forests, affecting tree growth (Chen and Luo 2015, Hogg et al. 2017), mortality
143 (Michaelian et al. 2010, Peng et al. 2011), wildfire (Jain et al. 2022), and insect outbreaks
144 (Boucher et al. 2018).

145

146 We used the gradient method (Loarie et al. 2009) rather than the climate-analog method
147 (Hamann et al. 2015) due to its interpretability and its ability to partition velocity into spatial and

148 temporal components. Our objective was to compare spatial patterns of PET-based climate
149 velocity and its components across alternative climate products, downscaling methods, and
150 GCMs, and to quantify the relative importance of these factors in explaining PET velocity. We
151 also examined how these relationships vary with local landscape context, including the
152 proportion of lakes in an area and topographic slope.

153

154 **Methods**

155

156 **Study Area**

157 Our analysis focused on the North American boreal forest biome (Figure 1), delineated using
158 Level II Terrestrial Ecoregions from the Commission for Environmental Cooperation (CEC
159 2009). We included the following ecoregions: 3.1 Alaska Boreal Interior, 3.2 Taiga Cordillera,
160 3.3 Taiga Plains, 3.4 Taiga Shield, 4.1 Hudson Plains, 5.1 Softwood Shield, and 6.1 Boreal
161 Cordillera.

162

163 **Climate data and baseline climatologies**

164 We calculated annual potential evapotranspiration (PET) from monthly temperature and
165 precipitation projections using Hogg's (1997) modified Penman–Monteith method. To compare
166 different baseline representations, we selected three products: (1) ClimateNA (Wang et al. 2016),
167 representing weather-station interpolation; (2) ERA5 (Hersbach et al. 2020), representing model-
168 based data assimilation; and (3) CRCM5 (Martynov et al. 2012), a regional climate model
169 simulation.

170

171 Visual comparisons (Figure 2a–f) showed that ClimateNA and other interpolation-based
172 products (e.g., DAYMET; Thornton et al. 2017, Canadian Forest Service gridded datasets;
173 McKenney et al. 2006) had similar PET patterns (Figure 2a–c). Likewise, model-based
174 climatologies—ERA5, CHELSA downscaling of ERA5 (Karger et al. 2017, 2018), and
175 CRCM5—displayed similar patterns around major lakes due to the common use of a lake model
176 (Martynov et al. 2012; Figure 2d–f). However, absolute PET values differed among products,
177 with CRCM5 exhibiting a consistent warm bias. Correlation analyses confirmed high agreement
178 within each product group (Table 1). We briefly describe each product below.

179 ***ClimateNA***. ClimateNA v7.30 (Wang et al. 2016) generates high-resolution historical and
180 projected climate data for North America. It uses CRU-TS2.1 1961–1990 normals (~10', ~18
181 km) as the baseline climatology, combined with CRU-TS time-series observations (0.5°) and
182 GCM anomalies (1°). Monthly surfaces are generated with a modified delta method, bilinear
183 interpolation, and elevation-based lapse rate adjustments. Baseline interpolation methods include
184 PRISM (Daly et al. 2008) for the conterminous U.S. and western Canada, and ANUSPLIN
185 (Hutchinson 2000) elsewhere, as represented in WorldClim (Hijmans et al. 2005; Fick &
186 Hijmans 2017). We used the 1-km version for CMIP5 provided by AdaptWest
187 (<https://adaptwest.databasin.org/pages/adaptwest-climatena-cmip5/>).

188 ***ERA5***. Native ERA5 monthly reanalysis data (0.25°, ~28 km) were obtained from the ECMWF /
189 Copernicus Climate Change Service (Hersbach et al. 2020). ERA5 assimilates a wide range of in
190 situ and satellite observations into a numerical weather prediction model, providing globally
191 complete, physically consistent climate fields.

192 **CRCM5**. The fifth-generation Canadian Regional Climate Model (CRCM5; Martynov et al.
193 2012; Šeparović et al. 2013), developed at UQÀM within the CORDEX initiative (Giorgi et al.
194 2009), is based on Environment and Climate Change Canada’s GEM numerical weather
195 prediction model version 3.3.3.1. CRCM5 incorporates parameterizations such as the FLake
196 freshwater lake model (Mironov et al. 2010; Martynov et al. 2012) and CLASS v3.5 (Verseghy
197 1991, 2009). Simulations were run at $\sim 0.22^\circ$ (~ 25 km) on a rotated latitude–longitude grid and
198 reprojected to a Lambert conformal conic projection with 22-km cells.

199

200 **Spatial resolution, global climate models, and downscaling**

201 To distinguish regional versus local spatial effects, all products were resampled to (1) the 22-km
202 native resolution of CRCM5 using bilinear interpolation, and (2) 1-km resolution using the
203 ClimateNA topographic adjustment algorithm (Wang et al. 2016), which produced the ERA5-
204 ClimNA and CRCM5-ClimNA versions used in our fine-resolution analyses. This algorithm
205 applies elevation-based lapse rates derived from linear regressions of temperature and elevation
206 using weather stations within a locally defined search radius, allowing the downscaling to reflect
207 fine-scale topographic variation (Wang et al. 2016).

208

209 We used three CMIP5 GCMs that served as inputs for statistical and dynamical downscaling:
210 CanESM2 (Arora et al. 2011), MPI-ESM-LR (Giorgetta et al. 2013), and CNRM-CM5 (Voltaire
211 et al. 2012). Following the delta method, statistically downscaled projections were generated by
212 adding GCM anomalies to the ClimateNA-R (22-km), ClimateNA (1-km), ERA5 (22-km), and
213 ERA5-ClimNA (1-km) baselines (scenarios 1–12, Table 2). These were compared with
214 dynamically downscaled CRCM5 simulations (scenarios 13–18). CRCM5 simulations used the

215 first ensemble member of each GCM, whereas statistical downscaling, which was based on
216 ClimateNA anomalies, averaged up to five members (Wang et al. 2016).

217

218 We focused on 2071–2100 under RCP 8.5, which is widely regarded as an extreme forcing
219 scenario (Hausfather and Peters 2020) but was used here to provide a clear signal for comparing
220 spatial patterns among products. CMIP5 was used because CRCM5 runs using CMIP6 data
221 (Paquin et al. 2025) were not consistently available or reviewed when this study began.

222

223 To assess the influence of local landscape context on PET velocity, we calculated two additional
224 metrics: lake fraction and slope. Lake fraction was calculated as the percent of each grid cell
225 covered by lakes. To capture potential spillover effects into surrounding cells, we used the
226 focal() function in the raster package (Hijmans 2023) in R v4.2.2 (R Core Team 2022) to
227 compute a 5×5 cell moving-window average. Slope in degrees was calculated using a 3×3 cell
228 neighborhood using elevation data from the corresponding grid resolution (1 km or 22 km).

229

230 **Climate velocity calculations**

231 For each spatial resolution, baseline climatology, downscaling approach, and GCM we
232 calculated PET velocity and its components (temporal and spatial gradients) using the ‘VoCC’
233 package (Garcia Molinos et al. 2019) in R v4.2.2 (R Core Team 2022). We applied the gradient
234 velocity method of Loarie et al. (2009), modified by Burrows et al. (2011):

235

236 $v = SG / TG$, where:

237 v = climate velocity (km yr⁻¹)

238 SG = spatial gradient (mm km⁻¹)

239 TG = temporal gradient (mm yr⁻¹)

240

241 The temporal gradient for each pixel was calculated as the mean projected change between
242 1981–2010 and the future period (2071–2100), divided by the number of years between
243 midpoints (e.g., 2085–1995 = 90 years). Spatial gradients were calculated with the spatGrad()
244 function as the vector sum of pairwise gradients within a 3×3 cell neighborhood, using baseline
245 PET means. We set a minimum SG threshold of 0.03 mm km⁻¹ to avoid infinite velocities. In this
246 formulation, the temporal gradient (TG) reflects the projected pace of PET change at a location,
247 whereas the spatial gradient (SG) represents the local climatic heterogeneity that can either
248 amplify or dampen resulting velocity values.

249

250 **Analysis of variance**

251 To partition variance in PET velocity, we fit separate Gaussian GLMs for each resolution (1 km,
252 22 km), thereby avoiding overparameterized interactions. To compare outputs across spatial
253 resolutions, the 22-km raster was converted to point data representing cell centroids. These
254 coordinates were then used to extract the corresponding values from the 1-km raster, allowing
255 direct resolution-based comparison. Predictors included baseline representation, downscaling
256 method, and GCM (categorical), plus lake fraction and slope (continuous). Interactions were
257 included between lake fraction and each categorical factor. We set the weather-station product as
258 the reference baseline representation, statistical downscaling as the reference downscaling

259 method, and CanESM2 as the reference GCM. We then performed ANOVA with Type III sums
260 of squares using the ‘car’ package (Fox & Weisberg 2019) in R v4.2.2 (R Core Team 2022).

261

262 **Results**

263

264 **Spatial patterns of PET and velocity components**

265 Spatial patterns of future potential evapotranspiration (PET) and its temporal gradient were
266 broadly consistent among general circulation models (GCMs) but were generally larger and
267 steeper for CanESM2 than for MPI-ESM-LR or CNRM-CM5 (Figure 3). The spatial gradient of
268 PET showed similar geographic patterns across all baseline representations, with the steepest
269 gradients in mountainous regions (Figure 4).

270

271 At 1-km resolution, the ClimateNA baseline did not capture the stronger spatial PET gradients
272 observed around large lakes in the model-based products ERA5-ClimNA and CRCM5-ClimNA
273 (Figure 4). With respect to the GCM downscaling method, dynamical downscaling (CRCM5-
274 ClimNA) produced relatively lower temporal gradients near lakes compared with statistical,
275 delta-method downscaling (ClimateNA and ERA5-ClimNA). The resulting PET-velocity
276 patterns were visually similar across products, with ERA5-ClimNA and CRCM5-ClimNA most
277 closely resembling one another (Figure 4, Figure S1). ClimateNA showed lower velocity values
278 in mountainous areas, whereas ERA5-ClimNA and CRCM5-ClimNA showed lower velocities in
279 lake-rich regions.

280

281 At the coarser 22-km resolution, overall spatial patterns were similar; however, spatial gradients
282 were larger in magnitude, leading to proportionally lower velocity values (Figure S2). Temporal
283 gradients were largely unchanged across resolutions, as expected from their definition.

284

285 When PET velocity was compared across the three climate products and GCMs at 1-km
286 resolution, CanESM2 produced higher overall velocities than the other two models (Figure S2).

287 Across GCMs, the station-based ClimateNA baseline yielded higher velocities in lake-rich
288 regions than did the model-based baselines (ERA5 and CRCM5), which displayed lower
289 velocities around large lakes.

290

291 **Modelled effects on PET velocity**

292 Modelled effects on PET velocity were dominated by baseline representation and
293 downscaling method (Table 3). At 1-km resolution, these two factors had the largest
294 standardized coefficients ($|\text{Std. } \beta| \approx 1.4\text{--}1.5$) and F-values ($> 200\ 000$), far exceeding those of
295 all other predictors. Model-based climatologies predicted higher PET velocities than the
296 station-interpolated baseline, whereas dynamical downscaling (CRCM5) produced
297 substantially lower velocities than statistical (delta-method) downscaling. Among GCMs,
298 CanESM2 yielded the highest velocities, followed by MPI-ESM-LR and CNRM-CM5,
299 consistent with the map patterns (Figure S2).

300

301 Slope exerted a strong negative influence ($\text{Std. } \beta = -0.26$), indicating lower velocities in steep
302 terrain. Lake fraction alone explained little variance, but interaction terms revealed significant

303 moderation of baseline and downscaling effects near lakes. Specifically, model-based baselines
304 showed steeper velocity reductions in lake-rich cells ($\beta = -0.071$, $p < 0.001$), whereas the
305 positive interaction between dynamical downscaling and lake fraction ($\beta = 0.087$, $p < 0.001$)
306 indicated that the negative effect of dynamical downscaling on PET velocity decreased with
307 increasing lake fraction.

308

309 At 22-km resolution, the same hierarchy of effects was evident but attenuated in magnitude
310 ($|\text{Std. } \beta| \leq 0.35$). Baseline type, downscaling method, slope, and GCM all remained highly
311 significant, whereas interactions with lake fraction were smaller and less consistent. The
312 ANOVA confirmed that baseline and downscaling together accounted for most of the
313 explained variance at both scales, with topography and GCM contributing secondarily and
314 lake variables explaining $< 1\%$.

315

316 **Discussion**

317 We compared climate velocity for the North American boreal biome across three contrasting
318 climate products—station-interpolated ClimateNA, the ERA5 reanalysis, and the CRCM5
319 regional climate model—using three GCMs. We specifically focused on annual potential
320 evapotranspiration (PET), a strongly temperature-driven indicator of drought exposure in boreal
321 forests, where warming has already intensified moisture stress (e.g., Peng et al. 2011; Price et al.
322 2013). Across products, differences in PET velocity were mostly explained by baseline
323 representation and downscaling method, while differences among GCMs were comparatively
324 modest. This pattern reflects the strong influence of spatial temperature gradients—including

325 those generated by large lakes—on gradient-based velocity metrics, which makes velocity more
326 sensitive to how baseline heterogeneity is represented than to variation among GCM projections.

327

328 Model-based baselines (ERA5 and CRCM5) produced higher average PET velocities than the
329 station-interpolated ClimateNA product, reflecting underlying differences in how spatial
330 gradients are represented. ClimateNA’s baseline incorporates steep topography-driven gradients
331 derived from weather-station interpolation and lapse-rate adjustments, which tend to reduce
332 climate velocity across mountainous regions. In contrast, model-based products depict smoother
333 terrain-related gradients but stronger lake-mediated gradients, yielding higher average velocities
334 across the study area. These lake-related gradients arise from explicit representation of lake–
335 atmosphere coupling processes that are well documented for large inland water bodies (Scott and
336 Huff 1996; Sellers et al. 1997; Austin and Colman 2007) but are not effectively captured by
337 sparse weather-station networks used in statistical downscaling. The mapped spatial patterns
338 reflect these differences, with steep elevational gradients dominating in ClimateNA and more
339 pronounced lake–land thermal contrasts in model-based products.

340

341 The lake-fraction interactions illustrate how these baseline differences play out across lake-rich
342 landscapes. The negative interaction between model-based baselines and lake fraction indicates
343 that velocity reductions near lakes are stronger in model-based products than in ClimateNA. In
344 other words, although model-based baselines produce higher PET velocities on average, they
345 also capture substantial local decreases in velocity in lake-dense regions, consistent with the
346 enhanced spatial temperature gradients simulated around large inland water bodies. These
347 localized reductions align with field and modeling evidence showing persistent lake-driven

348 temperature moderation and along-shore cooling effects extending several kilometers inland
349 (e.g., Sun et al. 1997; Irambona et al. 2018; Hillman and Nielsen 2023, 2025).

350

351 Dynamical downscaling (CRCM5) yielded lower PET velocities overall than the statistical delta-
352 method approach. Downscaling primarily influences the temporal gradient—particularly near
353 lakes, where CRCM5 simulates reduced future warming—and this lower temporal gradient
354 contributes to reduced velocity. The positive interaction between dynamical downscaling and
355 lake fraction reflects the shared model-based baseline between ERA5 and CRCM5, indicating
356 that the downscaling effect weakens slightly in lake-rich areas once baseline differences are
357 accounted for. Because spatial gradients dominate the velocity calculation, baseline
358 representation exerts a stronger overall influence than differences in downscaling approach.

359

360 Slope also exerted a strong negative influence on PET velocity, confirming the dominant role of
361 elevational gradients in shaping spatial temperature patterns in the boreal cordillera. Nonetheless,
362 lake-associated contrasts remained clearly visible—especially in model-based products that
363 explicitly represent lake–atmosphere interactions—suggesting that these products are better able
364 to retain lake-driven spatial temperature gradients that are not captured by topography alone.
365 Both slope and lake-fraction effects were strongest at 1-km resolution and diminished at 22-km,
366 consistent with the expected loss of fine-scale heterogeneity at coarser spatial scales.

367

368 Although the influence of lakes on regional climate is well documented in some areas, such as
369 the Laurentian Great Lakes (Changnon and Jones 1972; Notaro et al. 2013; Gula and Peltier
370 2012), fewer studies have examined comparable effects across the broader boreal region. Our

371 maps show reduced PET velocity near major boreal lakes—especially Great Slave, Great Bear,
372 and Winnipeg—as well as around some large reservoirs in eastern Canada, consistent with field
373 and modelling studies demonstrating summer cooling extending several kilometers inland.
374 Empirical measurements from Hillman and Nielsen (2023, 2025) confirm measurable nearshore
375 cooling for boreal lakes, driven by lake orientation, depth, and surrounding topography. While
376 the inland reach of small-lake breezes is typically limited to less than the lake diameter (Crosman
377 and Horel 2012), the cumulative influence of many small lakes may produce significant regional
378 moderation (Macdonald et al. 2006).

379

380 **Implications for climatic stability and drought vulnerability**

381 Because PET reflects the temperature-driven component of evaporative demand, lower PET
382 velocities near lakes indicate slower increases in atmospheric drying power in these regions.
383 Although our analysis focused on PET alone, the broader climate-moisture index ($CMI = P -$
384 PET ; Hogg 1997) provides additional context for interpreting drought vulnerability. Projected
385 increases in precipitation for much of the boreal zone (Price et al. 2013) may offset rising
386 evaporative demand where lake-moderated temperatures prevail, reducing drought severity and
387 helping maintain a positive water balance in some regions. In the western boreal zone, where
388 negative CMI values are expected by the late century, proximity to large lakes could help
389 maintain relatively cooler and moister microclimates that mitigate vegetation stress. Such areas
390 may therefore represent potential macro- and meso-scale climate-change refugia (Stralberg et al.
391 2020).

392

393 The close correspondence between ERA5 and CRCM5 in representing these patterns supports
394 the use of physically based climatologies for identifying spatial gradients in exposure, whereas
395 statistically downscaled, station-interpolated products may overestimate the pace of change in
396 lake-rich landscapes. Incorporating model-based climate baselines that account for lake-
397 atmosphere coupling can thus improve assessments of climatic stability in northern regions
398 where observation networks are sparse.

399

400 **Limitations and future directions**

401 Several limitations merit consideration. Our analysis examined annual PET under the high-
402 emission RCP 8.5 scenario, offering a consistent comparison but representing an upper bound on
403 future change. The CRCM5 simulations used CMIP5 forcing; new CMIP6-driven regional
404 models (Paquin et al. 2025) will enable further testing of these findings. CRCM5 also exhibits a
405 modest warm bias in parts of northern Canada (Šeparović et al. 2013; Irambona et al. 2018),
406 though its agreement with ERA5 suggests that spatial patterns are robust.

407

408 A further limitation is the partial confounding between baseline representation and downscaling
409 method in our experimental design: ERA5 shares a model-based baseline with CRCM5 but uses
410 statistical downscaling, which makes it difficult to fully isolate the independent effects of
411 baseline type and downscaling approach on PET velocity and contributes to the mixed signs of
412 lake-fraction interactions.

413

414 Furthermore, our analysis was not designed to resolve fine-scale shoreline or small-lake effects.
415 Field data from Hillman and Nielsen (2023, 2025) indicate that observed summer cooling near

416 large lakes is somewhat smaller and more localized than suggested by model-based
417 climatologies. Expanding networks of temperature loggers around major and mid-sized lakes—
418 especially in under-instrumented northern regions—would allow empirical validation of
419 modelled lake effects and refinement of interpolation and downscaling algorithms.

420

421 Finally, the persistence of lake-driven buffering under continued warming remains uncertain.

422 Many lakes are warming faster than their surrounding land surfaces owing to earlier ice-off,
423 reduced mixing, and higher solar absorption (O'Reilly et al. 2015; Woolway et al. 2020). As the
424 temperature difference between lakes and nearby land shrinks, their cooling influence may
425 weaken; alternatively, if land warms faster than water—particularly at high latitudes—stronger
426 lake–land temperature contrasts could enhance lake-breeze effects and the movement of cooler
427 air inland. Resolving these opposing possibilities will require tighter integration of physical lake
428 models with regional climate simulations, supported by expanded field observations.

429

430 **Conclusions**

431 Large lakes appear to slow the pace of climatic change in surrounding boreal regions by
432 strengthening spatial temperature gradients and dampening temporal ones, resulting in lower
433 PET velocities and greater potential for climatic stability. These buffering effects—supported by
434 both modelled and field-measured temperature data—highlight the importance of large inland
435 waters as potential climate-change refugia. Incorporating model-based climatologies and
436 reanalysis products that explicitly represent lake–atmosphere interactions can improve the
437 realism of climate-exposure assessments in northern ecosystems where weather stations are
438 sparse. Continued empirical monitoring and refinement of high-resolution model baselines can

439 enhance the identification of lake-mediated refugia, supporting climate-informed conservation
440 and management across the boreal biome.

441

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454

455 **Competing interests**

456 The authors declare there are no competing interests.

457

458 **Data availability**

459 The geospatial datasets presented in this paper are available in a Zenodo repository:

460 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18066597>.

461

462

463 **References**

- 464 Arora VK, Scinocca JF, Boer GJ, et al (2011) Carbon emission limits required to satisfy future
465 representative concentration pathways of greenhouse gases. *Geophys Res Lett* 38:3–8.
466 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GL046270>
- 467 Boucher D, Boulanger Y, Aubin I, et al (2018) Current and projected cumulative impacts of fire,
468 drought and insects on timber volumes across Canada. *Ecol Appl* 28:1245–1259.
469 <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1724>
- 470 Boulanger Y, Pascual J, Bouchard M, et al (2022) Multi-model projections of tree species
471 performance in Quebec, Canada under future climate change. *Glob Chang Biol* 28:1884–
472 1902. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16014>
- 473 Briley LJ, Rood RB, Notaro M (2021) Large lakes in climate models: A Great Lakes case study
474 on the usability of CMIP5. *J Great Lakes Res* 47:405–418.
475 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jglr.2021.01.010>
- 476 Burrows MT, Schoeman DS, Buckley LB, et al (2011) The Pace of Shifting Climate in Marine
477 and Terrestrial Ecosystems. *Science* 334:652–655.
478 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1210288>
- 479 Carroll C, Roberts DR, Michalak JL, et al (2017) Scale-dependent complementarity of climatic
480 velocity and environmental diversity for identifying priority areas for conservation under
481 climate change. *Glob Chang Biol* 23:4508–4520. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13679>
- 482 CEC (2009) Ecological Regions of North America. Commission for Environmental Cooperation.
483 www.cec.org/north-american-environmental-atlas/terrestrial-ecoregions-level-ii/.
- 484 Changnon SA, Jones DMA (1972) Review of the influences of the Great Lakes on weather.
485 *Water Resources Research* 8:360-371. <https://doi.org/10.1029/WR008i002p00360>

486 Chen HYH, Luo Y (2015) Net aboveground biomass declines of four major forest types with
487 forest ageing and climate change in western Canada's boreal forests. *Glob Chang Biol*
488 21:3675–3684. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12994>

489 Daly C (2006) Guidelines for assessing the suitability of spatial climate data sets. *Int J Climatol*
490 26: 707-721. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1322>

491 Daly C, Halbleib M, Smith JI, et al (2008) Physiographically sensitive mapping of climatological
492 temperature and precipitation across the conterminous United States. *Int J Climatol*
493 28:2031–2064. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1688>

494 Dobrowski SZ, Parks SA (2016) Climate change velocity underestimates climate change
495 exposure in mountainous regions. *Nat Commun* 7:12349.
496 <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms12349>

497 Essou GRC, Brissette F, Lucas-Picher P (2017) Impacts of combining reanalyses and weather
498 station data on the accuracy of discharge modelling. *Journal of Hydrology* 545:120-131.
499 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2016.12.021>

500 Faroux S, Kaptué Tchuenté AT, Roujean J-L, et al (2013) ECOCLIMAP-II/Europe: a twofold
501 database of ecosystems and surface parameters at 1 km resolution based on satellite
502 information for use in land surface, meteorological and climate models. *Geoscientific*
503 *Model Development* 6:563-582. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-6-563-2013>

504 Frelich LE, Montgomery RA, Reich PB (2021) Seven ways a warming climate can kill the
505 southern boreal forest. *Forests* 12:560. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f12050560>

506 Frelich LE (2002) *Forest dynamics and disturbance regimes: studies from temperate evergreen-*
507 *deciduous forests.* Cambridge University Press.

508 Fox J, Weisberg S. (2019). An R Companion to Applied Regression. Third edition. Sage,
509 Thousand Oaks, CA, USA. <https://www.john-fox.ca/Companion/>.

510 García Molinos J, Schoeman DS, Brown CJ, Burrows MT (2019) VoCC: An r package for
511 calculating the velocity of climate change and related climatic metrics. *Methods Ecol*
512 *Evol* 10:2195–2202. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13295>

513 Giorgetta MA, Jungclaus J, Reick CH, et al (2013) Climate and carbon cycle changes from 1850
514 to 2100 in MPI-ESM simulations for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase
515 5. *J Adv Model Earth Syst* 5:572–597. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jame.20038>

516 Giorgi F, Jones C, Asrar GR (2009) Addressing climate information needs at the regional level:
517 the CORDEX framework. *WMO Bulletin* 58:175–183.

518 Given DR, Soper JH (1981) The arctic-alpine element of the vascular flora at Lake Superior.
519 *Publications in Botany - National Museum of Natural Sciences*, Issue 10 (p.70).
520 <http://books.google.com/books?id=H4k9MgEACAAJ&pgis=1>

521 Goldblum D, Rigg LS (2010) The deciduous forest-boreal forest ecotone. *Geography Compass*
522 4: 707-717. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-8198.2010.00342.x>

523 Gorelick N, Hancher M, Dixon M, et al (2017) Google Earth Engine: Planetary-scale geospatial
524 analysis for everyone.

525 Gula J, Peltier WR (2012) Dynamical Downscaling over the Great Lakes Basin of North
526 America Using the WRF Regional Climate Model: The Impact of the Great Lakes
527 System on Regional Greenhouse Warming. *J Clim* 25:7723–7742.
528 <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-11-00388.1>

529 Hamann A, Roberts D, Barber Q, et al (2015) Velocity of climate change algorithms for guiding
530 conservation and management. *Glob Chang Biol* 21:997–1004.
531 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12736>

532 Hausfather Z, Peters GP (2020) Emissions – the “business as usual” story is misleading. *Nature*
533 577:618–620. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00177-3>

534 Hersbach H, Bell B, Berrisford P, et al (2020) The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Q J R Meteorol Soc*
535 146: 1999– 2049. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>

536 Hijmans R (2025) Raster: Geographic Data Analysis and Modeling. R package version 3.6-
537 32, <https://github.com/rspatial/raster>.

538 Hijmans RJ, Cameron SE, Parra JL, Jones PG, Jarvis A (2005) Very high resolution interpolated
539 climate surfaces for global land areas. *International Journal of Climatology* 25:1965–
540 1978. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1276>

541 Hillman A, Nielsen SE (2023) Lake Superior’s summer cooling of shorelines and adjacent inland
542 forests: Implications for refugia of boreal forests and disjunct arctic-alpine plants.
543 *Ecology and Evolution* 13:1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10833>

544 Hillman A, Nielsen SE (2024) Climate refugia along Lake Superior’s shores: disjunct arctic–
545 alpine plants rely on cool shoreline temperatures but are restricted to highly exposed
546 habitat under climate warming. *Journal of Plant Ecology* 17:rtae050.
547 <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpe/rtae050>

548 Hillman A, Nielsen SE (2025) Climate buffering effects of western Canadian boreal lakes: the
549 effect of lake size and depth on shoreline and nearshore forests. *Landscape Ecology* 40:
550 124. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-025-02146-5>

551 Hinkel KM, Nelson FE (2012) Spatial and temporal aspects of the lake effect on the southern
552 shore of Lake Superior. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology* 109:415-428.
553 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-012-0585-2>

554 Hogg EH, Michaelian M, Hook TI, Undershultz ME (2017) Recent climatic drying leads to age-
555 independent growth reductions of white spruce stands in western Canada. *Glob Chang*
556 *Biol* 23:5297–5308. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13795>

557 Hostetler SW, Bates GT, Giorgi F (1993) Interactive coupling of a lake thermal model with a
558 regional climate model. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 98:5045-5057.

559 Hutchinson MF (2000) ANUSPLIN Version 4.1 User Guide. Centre for Resource and
560 Environmental Studies, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia

561 Irambona C, Music B, Nadeau DF, et al (2018) Impacts of boreal hydroelectric reservoirs on
562 seasonal climate and precipitation recycling as simulated by the CRCM5: a case study of
563 the La Grande River watershed, Canada. *Theor Appl Climatol* 131:1529–1544.
564 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-016-2010-8>

565 Jain P, Castellanos-Acuna D, Coogan SCP et al. (2022) Observed increases in extreme fire
566 weather driven by atmospheric humidity and temperature. *Nat Clim Chang* 12:63–70.
567 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01224-1>

568 Karger DN, Conrad O, Böhrner J, Kawohl T, Kreft H, Soria-Auza RW, Zimmermann NE,
569 Lindert, H.P., Kessler, M. (2018): Data from: Climatologies at high resolution for the
570 earth’s land surface areas. *EnviDat*. <https://doi.org/10.16904/envidat.228.v2.1>

571 Karger DN, Lange S, Hari C, Reyer CPO, Zimmermann NE (2021): CHELSA-W5E5 v1.1:
572 W5E5 v1.0 downscaled with CHELSA v2.0. ISIMIP Repository.
573 <https://doi.org/10.48364/ISIMIP.836809.1>

574 Kopec RJ (1967) Areal patterns of seasonal temperature anomalies in the vicinity of the Great
575 Lakes. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 48:884-889.
576 <https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477-48.12.884>

577 Macdonald E, Eaton B, Machtans CS, Paszkowski C, Hannon S, Boutin S (2006) Is forest close
578 to lakes ecologically unique? Analysis of vegetation, small mammals, amphibians, and
579 songbirds. *Forest Ecology and Management* 223: 1-17.
580 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2005.06.017>

581 Martynov A, Sushama L, Laprise R, et al (2012) Interactive lakes in the Canadian Regional
582 Climate Model, version 5: the role of lakes in the regional climate of North America.
583 *Tellus A Dyn Meteorol Oceanogr* 64:16226. <https://doi.org/10.3402/tellusa.v64i0.16226>

584 McElhinny M, Beckers JF, Hanes C, et al (2020) A high-resolution reanalysis of global fire
585 weather from 1979 to 2018 – overwintering the Drought Code. *Earth Syst Sci Data*
586 12:1823–1833. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-1823-2020>

587 Meunier C, Sirois L, Bégin Y (2007) Climate and *Picea mariana* seed maturation relationships: a
588 multi-scale perspective. *Ecol Monogr* 77:361–376. <https://doi.org/10.1890/06-1543.1>

589 Michaelian M, Hogg EH, Hall RJ, Arsenault E (2010) Massive mortality of aspen following
590 severe drought along the southern edge of the Canadian boreal forest. *Glob Chang Biol*
591 17:2084–2094

592 Mironov D, Heise E, Kourzeneva E, et al (2010) Implementation of the lake parameterisation
593 scheme FLake into the numerical weather prediction model COSMO. *Boreal Environmental*
594 *Research* 15:218-230.

595 Noël T, Loukos H, Defrance D, et al (2022) Extending the global high-resolution downscaled
596 projections dataset to include CMIP6 projections at increased resolution coherent with the
597 ERA5-Land reanalysis. Data Br 45:108669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.108669>

598 Notaro M, Holman K, Zarrin A, et al (2013) Influence of the Laurentian Great Lakes on
599 Regional Climate. J Clim 26:789–804. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-12-00140.1>

600 Ordonez A, Martinuzzi S, Radeloff VC, Williams JW (2014) Combined speeds of climate and
601 land-use change of the conterminous US until 2050. Nat Clim Chang 4:811–816.
602 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2337>

603 O'Reilly CM, Sharma S, Gray DK, et al (2015) Rapid and highly variable warming of lake
604 surface waters around the globe. Geophys Res Lett 42:10,710-773,781.
605 <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GL066235>

606 Paquin D, McCray C, Gauthier CB, Giguère M, Asselin O, Bourgault P, Labonté MP, Matte D
607 (2025) The Ouranos CRCM5-CMIP6 ensemble: A dynamically downscaled ensemble of
608 CMIP6 simulations over North America. Scientific Data. [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-06289-7)
609 [025-06289-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-06289-7)

610 Peng C, Ma Z, Lei X, et al (2011) A drought-induced pervasive increase in tree mortality across
611 Canada's boreal forests. Nat Clim Chang 1:467–471. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1293>

612 Plattner S, Mason DM, Leshkevich GA, et al (2006) Classifying and forecasting coastal
613 upwellings in Lake Michigan using satellite derived temperature images and buoy data. J
614 Great Lakes Res 32:63–76. [https://doi.org/10.3394/0380-](https://doi.org/10.3394/0380-1330(2006)32[63:CAFUI]2.0.CO;2)
615 [1330\(2006\)32\[63:CAFUI\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.3394/0380-1330(2006)32[63:CAFUI]2.0.CO;2)

616 Price DT, Alfaro RI, Brown KJ, et al (2013) Anticipating the consequences of climate change for
617 Canada's boreal forest ecosystems 1. *Environ Rev* 21:322–365. [https://doi.org/10.1139/er-](https://doi.org/10.1139/er-2013-0042)
618 [2013-0042](https://doi.org/10.1139/er-2013-0042)

619 R Core Team (2022) R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for
620 Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <http://www.R-project.org/>

621 Rotbarth R, Van Nes EH, Scheffer M et al (2023) Northern expansion is not compensating for
622 southern declines in North American boreal forests. *Nat Commun* 14:3373.
623 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39092-2>

624 Sánchez-Pinillos M, D'Orangeville L, Boulanger Y, et al (2022) Sequential droughts: A silent
625 trigger of boreal forest mortality. *Glob Chang Biol* 28:542–556.
626 <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15913>

627 Scheffer MN, Hirota M, Holmgren M, Van Nes EH, Chapin III FS (2012) Thresholds for boreal
628 biome transitions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 109:21384-21389.

629 Scott RW, Huff FA (1996) Impacts of the Great Lakes on Regional Climate Conditions. *J Great*
630 *Lakes Res* 22:845–863. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0380-1330\(96\)71006-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0380-1330(96)71006-7)

631 Sellers PJ, Hall FG, Kelly RD, et al (1997) BOREAS in 1997: Experiment overview, scientific
632 results, and future directions. *J Geophys Res Atmos* 102:28731–28769.
633 <https://doi.org/10.1029/97JD03300>

634 Šeparović L, Alexandru A, Laprise R, et al (2013) Present climate and climate change over
635 North America as simulated by the fifth-generation Canadian regional climate model. *Clim*
636 *Dyn* 41:3167–3201. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-013-1737-5>

637 Shen J (1998). Numerical Modelling of the Effects of Vegetation and Environmental Conditions
638 on the Lake Breeze. *Boundary-Layer Meteorology*, 87(3), 481–498.
639 <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1000906300218>

640 Song Y, Sass-Klaassen U, Sterck F, Goudzwaard L, Akhmetzyanov L, Poorter L (2021) Growth
641 of 19 conifer species is highly sensitive to winter warming, spring frost, and summer
642 drought. *Annals of Botany* 128: 545-557.

643 Soper JH, Maycock PF (1963) A community of arctic-alpine plants on the east shore of Lake
644 Superior. *Can J Bot* 41:183–198. <https://doi.org/10.1139/b63-016>

645 Stralberg D, Arsenault D, Barber Q, et al. (2020) Climate-change refugia in boreal North
646 America: what, where, and for how long? *Front Ecol Environ* 18(5): 261– 270.
647 <http://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2188>

648 Sun J, Lenschow DH, Mahrt L, et al (1997) Lake-induced atmospheric circulations during
649 BOREAS. *J Geophys Res Atmos* 102:29155–29166. <https://doi.org/10.1029/97JD01114>

650 Sun L, Jaramillo F, Cai Y, et al (2021) Exploring the influence of reservoir impoundment on
651 surrounding tree growth. *Adv Water Resour* 153:103946.
652 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2021.103946>

653 Taylor KE, Stouffer RJ, Meehl GA (2012) An Overview of CMIP5 and the Experiment Design.
654 *Bull Am Meteorol Soc* 93:485–498. <https://doi.org/10.1175/bams-d-11-00094.1>

655 Therneau T, Atkinson B, Ripley B (2022) rpart: Recursive Partitioning and Regression Trees. R
656 package version 4.1.19. R Core Team. R Foundation for statistical computing, Vienna
657 Austria. <http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rpart>

658 Thornton MM, Shrestha R, Wei Y, Thornton PE, Kao SC (2022). Daymet: Annual Climate
659 Summaries on a 1-km Grid for North America, Version 4 R1. ORNL DAAC, Oak Ridge,
660 Tennessee, USA. <https://doi.org/10.3334/ORNLDAAC/2130>

661 Tremblay M, Bègin Y (2000) The response of black spruce to the climatic influence of Robert-
662 Bourassa Reservoir in northern Québec. *Écoscience* 7:228–236.
663 <https://doi.org/10.1080/11956860.2000.11682592>

664 USGS EROS Archive (2018a) Land Cover Products - Global Land Cover Characterization
665 (GLCC). A global land cover database primarily derived from 1992 to 1993 1-km
666 AVHRR data. <https://doi.org/10.5066/F7GB230D>

667 USGS EROS Archive (2018b) Digital Elevation - Global 30 Arc-Second Elevation (GTOPO30).
668 <https://doi.org/10.5066/F7DF6PQS>

669 Versegny DL (1991) CLASS—A Canadian land surface scheme for GCMs. I. Soil model.
670 *International Journal of Climatology*, 11(2), 111–133.

671 Versegny DL (2009) CLASS—The Canadian Land Surface Scheme (version 3.4) technical
672 documentation (version 1.1), Environment Canada. Climate Research Division, Science
673 and Technology Branch, Downsview, Ontario, Canada.

674 Voldoire A, Sanchez-Gomez E, Salas y Mélia D, et al (2013) The CNRM-CM5.1 global climate
675 model: description and basic evaluation. *Clim Dyn* 40:2091–2121.
676 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-011-1259-y>

677 Wan Z, Hook S, Hulley G (2015) MOD11A1 MODIS/Terra Land Surface
678 Temperature/Emissivity Daily L3 Global 1km SIN Grid V006 [Data set]. NASA
679 EOSDIS Land Processes DAAC. Accessed 2022-03-17 from
680 <https://doi.org/10.5067/MODIS/MOD11A1.006>

681 Wang J, Taylor AR, D'Orangeville L (2023) Warming-induced tree growth may help offset
682 increasing disturbance across the Canadian boreal forest. Proc Natl Acad Sci
683 120:e2212780120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2212780120>

684 Wang T, Hamann A, Spittlehouse D, Carroll C (2016b) Locally Downscaled and Spatially
685 Customizable Climate Data for Historical and Future Periods for North America. PLoS
686 One 11:e0156720. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0156720>

687 Warren RJ, Vermette S (2022) Laurentian Great Lakes warming threatens northern fruit belt
688 refugia. Int J Biometeorol. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-021-02226-6>

689 Woolway RI, Kraemer BM, Lenters JD, et al (2020) Global lake responses to climate change.
690 Nat Rev Earth Environ 1:388–403. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-020-0067-5>

691 WMO (2011) Guide to climatological practices. World Meteorological Organization Rep. 100,
692 117 pp.

693

694

695 **Table captions**

696

697 **Table 1.** Pearson correlations among different representations of potential evapotranspiration
698 (PET, mm/yr) on a 22-km grid from six historical (1981-2010) baselines: (a) Canadian Regional
699 Climate Model v. 5 (CRCM5) simulated based on boundary conditions derived from the
700 CanESM2 GCM (Martynov et al. 2012); (b) ERA5 5th generation ECMWF atmospheric
701 reanalysis, resampled from native $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid (Hersbach et al. 2020), (e) CHELSA high-
702 resolution climatology resampled from native 1-km grid (Karger et al. 2018), (d) ClimateNA
703 resampled from native 1-km grid (Wang et al. 2016), (e) Daymet climate data resampled from
704 native 1-km grid (Thornton et al. 2022), (f) Canadian Forest Service (CFS) climate data
705 resampled from native 1-km grid (McKenney et al. 2011).

706

707 **Table 2:** Unique combinations of baseline representation, downscaling method, global climate
708 model, and spatial resolution for which the climate velocity of potential evapotranspiration (PET,
709 mm/yr) was evaluated. ERA5 = 5th generation ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis. CRCM5 =
710 Canadian Regional Climate Model v. 5.

711

712 **Table 3:** Modelled effects on PET velocity at 1-km and 22-km resolution. *F*-values, Beta
713 coefficients (β), standardized beta coefficients (Std. β), and standard error (SE) are provided for
714 the effects of baseline representation, downscaling method, global climate model, fraction of
715 lakes in a 5×5 -km neighbourhood, slope, and lake-fraction interactions. Reference categories
716 are shown in parentheses.

717

718 **Figure captions**

719

720 **Figure 1.** North American boreal region with major lakes identified.

721

722 **Figure 2.** Comparison of historical (1981-2010) potential evapotranspiration (PET, mm yr⁻¹) on
723 a 22-km grid from six historical baselines: (a) ClimateNA resampled from native 1-km grid
724 (Wang et al. 2016); (b) Daymet climate data resampled from native 1-km grid (Thornton et al.
725 2022); (c) Canadian Forest Service (CFS) climate data resampled from native 1-km grid
726 (McKenney et al. 2011); (d) Canadian Regional Climate Model v. 5 (CRCM5) simulated at
727 ~0.22° resolution based on boundary conditions derived from the CanESM2 GCM (Martynov et
728 al. 2012); (e) ERA5 5th generation ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis, resampled from native
729 0.25° grid (Hersbach et al. 2020); and (f) CHELSA high-resolution climatology resampled from
730 native 1-km grid (Karger et al. 2018).

731

732 **Figure 3.** Comparison of dynamically downscaled projected future (2071-2100, RCP 8.5)
733 potential evapotranspiration (PET, mm, first column) and temporal gradient (mm yr⁻¹, second
734 column) on a 22-km grid based on three different GCMs inputs to the CRCM5 regional climate
735 model (see Table 2). Top row: CanESM2; Middle row: MPI-ESM-LR; Bottom row: CNRM-
736 CM5.

737

738 **Figure 4.** Velocity components (columns) for three different climate products (rows) at 1-km
739 resolution. Top row: ClimateNA; Middle row: ERA5-ClimNA; Bottom row: CRCM5-ClimNA
740 (see Table 2). First column: log₁₀(spatial gradient, mm km⁻¹) for 1981-2010 baseline period;

741 Second column: temporal gradient (mm yr^{-1}) from baseline (1981-2010) to end-of- century
742 (2071-2100) based on CanESM2 (RCP 8.5); Third column: $\log_{10}(\text{velocity} + 1)$, where velocity
743 (km yr^{-1}) = temporal gradient / spatial gradient

744

745 **Figure 5.** Zoomed-in PET velocity for three climate products at 1-km spatial resolution: (A)
746 ClimateNA, (B) ERA5-ClimNA, and (c) CRCM5-ClimNA (see Table 2).

747

748 **Table 1.**

	CRCM5	ERA5	CHELSA	ClimateNA	Daymet	CFS
CRCM5	1	0.861	0.872	0.731	0.781	0.759
ERA5	0.861	1	0.980	0.901	0.905	0.912
CHELSA	0.872	0.980	1	0.896	0.910	0.915
ClimateNA	0.731	0.901	0.896	1	0.964	0.975
Daymet	0.781	0.905	0.910	0.964	1	0.979
CFS	0.759	0.912	0.915	0.975	0.979	1

749

750 **Table 2.**

Scenario	Climate Product	Baseline Representation	GCM Downscaling Method	GCM	Spatial Resolution
1	ClimateNA-R	Station-based	Statistical	CanESM2	22 km
2	ClimateNA	Station-based	Statistical	CanESM2	1 km
3	ClimateNA-R	Station-based	Statistical	MPI-ESM-LR	22 km
4	ClimateNA	Station-based	Statistical	MPI-ESM-LR	1 km
5	ClimateNA-R	Station-based	Statistical	CNRM-CM5	22 km
6	ClimateNA	Station-based	Statistical	CNRM-CM5	1 km
7	ERA5	Model-based	Statistical	CanESM2	22 km
8	ERA5-ClimNA	Model-based	Statistical	CanESM2	1 km
9	ERA5	Model-based	Statistical	MPI-ESM-LR	22 km
10	ERA5-ClimNA	Model-based	Statistical	MPI-ESM-LR	1 km
11	ERA5	Model-based	Statistical	CNRM-CM5	22 km
12	ERA5-ClimNA	Model-based	Statistical	CNRM-CM5	1 km
13	CRCM5	Model-based	Dynamical	CanESM2	22 km

14	CRCM5-ClimNA	Model-based	Dynamical	CanESM2	1 km
15	CRCM5	Model-based	Dynamical	MPI-ESM-LR	22 km
16	CRCM5-ClimNA	Model-based	Dynamical	MPI-ESM-LR	1 km
17	CRCM5	Model-based	Dynamical	CNRM-CM5	22 km
18	CRCM5-ClimNA	Model-based	Dynamical	CNRM-CM5	1 km

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752 **Table 3.**

Variable	<i>F</i> -value	1-km resolution		22-km resolution	
		β	Std. β (SE)	β	Std. β (SE)
Baseline representation (Station-based)	210604				
Model-based		34.43	1.469 (0.075)	1.884	0.202 (0.035)
Downscaling method (Statistical)	204088				
Dynamical		-33.89	-1.442 (0.075)	-2.655	-0.348 (0.035)
Global climate model (CanESM2)	7259				
CNRM-CR5		-7.617	-0.349 (0.075)	-2.988	-0.395 (0.032)
MPI-ESM-LR		-4.811	-0.231 (0.075)	-2.192	-0.290 (0.032)
Lake fraction (5×5 neighborhood)	1.28	-0.006	-0.003 (0.005)	-0.007	-0.011 (0.002)
Slope	45456	-1.209	-0.264 (0.006)	-0.328	-0.221 (0.003)
Baseline * Lake fraction	148				
Model-based		-0.071	-0.036 (0.006)	-0.070	-0.109 (0.003)

Downscaling * Lake fraction	223				
Dynamical		0.087	0.044 (0.006)	0.008	0.013 (0.003)
GCM * Lake fraction	222				
CNRM-CRS		-0.092	-0.046 (0.006)	0.004	0.007 (0.003)
MPI-ESM-LR		-0.101	-0.051 (0.006)	0.003	0.005 (0.003)
Intercept	31820	13.14	-0.030 (0.074)	8.775	0.209 (0.004)

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755 **Figures**

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758 **Figure 1.**

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761 **Figure 2.**

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764 **Figure 3.**

Figure 4.

Figure 5.